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Pseudocolus

Pseudocolus is a genus of basidiomycete fungi in the family Clathraceae.

NCBI Taxonomy ID

68806

Taxonomic rank

genus

Current scientific name

Pseudocolus

Lloyd, 1907

[View taxonomic details](#)

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Database links

Nucleotide

All nucleotide sequences 18

Genomic sequences 18

Lineage

[Eukaryota](#) (eucaryotes)

Domain

[Fungi](#)

Kingdom

[Basidiomycota](#)
(basidiomycetes)

Phylum

[Agaricomycetes](#)

Class

[Phallales](#)

Order

[Clathraceae](#)

Family

[View full lineage](#)

[Browse taxonomy](#)

External links

[Encyclopedia of Life](#)

mRNA sequences	0
----------------	---

Protein

Protein sequences	0
-------------------	---

Conserved domains	0
-------------------	---

3D structures	0
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From Type Material

Sequences	0
-----------	---

BioSample	0
-----------	---

Genome	0
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Sequence Read Archive (SRA)

All SRA experiments	1
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DNA	1
-----	---

RNA	0
-----	---

GEO Datasets

Datasets	0
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Series	0
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Samples	0
---------	---

Platforms	0
-----------	---

Projects and samples

BioProject	0
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BioSample	1
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